

Legal Framework for Income Distribution in Cooperatives: Principles and Practice

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Abstract

To conduct business activities, the first, cooperatives must have charter capital, which members contribute to the cooperative according to their commitment before establishment. The second, In the process of business activities, members must directly contribute labor, that is, participate in the management and operation of cooperative activities, at the same time, members directly use the products and services of the cooperative, create revenue, and ultimately create profits for the cooperative, generating income. When income arises, the cooperative processes the income according to the order and procedures prescribed by the Law on Cooperatives, according to the provisions in the Cooperative Charter or according to the financial regulations of the cooperative. Finally, the cooperative distributes income to members according to the level of use of products and services, according to the level of labor contribution and according to the capital contribution ratio.

Keywords: *income, distribute, income distribution, income distribution in cooperatives.*

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Make a Problem

The business results of a cooperative occur in one of the following three cases: (i) revenue is less than expenses, the cooperative makes a loss, so there is no income; (ii) revenue equals expenses, the cooperative breaks even, no income arises; (iii) revenue is greater than expenses, the cooperative makes a profit, and income arises.

Once the common fund has been allocated, the cooperative's income is not immediately distributed. Instead, it undergoes a series of financial processes in accordance with legal requirements. These include the payment of taxes, settlement of other financial obligations, and the management of any losses incurred from business or production activities. Additionally,

the cooperative sets aside legally mandated reserves (if applicable), as well as other funds as determined by the General Meeting of Members.

The income remaining after these deductions is then distributed among the cooperative's official and associate members. This distribution is based on several criteria: the extent of their use of the cooperative's products and services, the amount of labor they have contributed, and the proportion of capital they have invested. In this article, the author explores the approach used to allocate income between official and associate members who have made capital contributions within cooperative organizations (National Assembly of the Socialist Republic of Vietnam, 2023).

Research Content and Results

Legal Provisions on Income Distribution

When a cooperative generates income, it is processed in the following order:

First: Establishing an undivided common fund

An undivided common fund is a fund of the cooperative that is not distributed to members during its operation. The undivided common fund of the cooperative is formed from the following four sources:

First: Income from internal transactions of the cooperative is established annually at the rate prescribed by the Charter (National Assembly of the Socialist Republic of Vietnam, 2023);

Second: Income from external transactions of the cooperative; income from enterprises established by the cooperative; income from capital contributions and share purchases is established annually at the rate prescribed by the Charter but not lower than 5%.

Third: Income from the transfer and liquidation of undivided common assets is the State's support that is stipulated to be included in the undivided common assets and assets partially or fully supported by the State are stipulated to be undivided common assets (National Assembly of the Socialist Republic of Vietnam, 2023);

Fourth: Income from legal donations and sponsorships of individuals and organizations in Vietnamese Dong or foreign currency according to the agreement to be put into the common fund without sharing after completing tax payment obligations according to the provisions of law (Ministry of Financ, 2014).

If the cooperative has income from internal transactions, it is calculated as follows: Income from internal transactions of the cooperative is equal to ($=$) revenue from internal transactions minus ($-$) costs directly related to such internal transactions.

Internal transactions are understood as the provision of products and services including job creation services and internal lending activities of the cooperative to official members according to a written agreement (Government of Vietnam, 2024).

Income from external trading activities of the cooperative is equal to ($=$) revenue from external trading activities minus ($-$) costs directly related to external trading activities.

External transactions are transactions of the cooperative that are not internal transactions.

Second: Paying taxes, fulfilling other financial obligations and handling losses in production and business activities according to the provisions of law

The cooperative registers for tax, declares and pays corporate income tax at a tax rate of 20% (National Assembly of Vietnam, 2008), except for the business lines of the cooperative that are regulated by the law on corporate income tax as tax-exempt income (National Assembly of Vietnam, 2008).

If the cooperative incurs a loss, it can carry the loss forward to the following year, and this loss is deducted from taxable income. The period for carrying forward losses shall not exceed five years, starting from the year following the year in which the loss arises (National Assembly of Vietnam, 2008).

Third: Setting aside funds in accordance with the provisions of law (if any) and setting aside other funds as decided by the Members' Meeting (National Assembly of the Socialist Republic of Vietnam, 2023).

Funds decided by the Members' Meeting include welfare funds and reward funds

Fourth: Income distribution

The remaining income of the cooperative shall be distributed to official members and associate members contributing capital in the following order (National Assembly of the Socialist Republic of Vietnam, 2023):

(i) For the remaining income from internal transactions, at least 51% shall be distributed to official members according to the level of product and service usage and the level of labor contribution; the remaining portion shall be distributed according to the capital contribution ratio for official members and associate members contributing capital in accordance with the provisions of the Charter (National

Assembly of the Socialist Republic of Vietnam, 2023);

(ii) The remaining income from external transactions is distributed to official members and capital-contributing associate members according to the provisions of the Charter (National Assembly of the Socialist Republic of Vietnam, 2023).

Official members are in one of three cases: (i) Members contribute capital and use products and services of the cooperative; (ii) Members contribute capital and labor to the cooperative; (iii) Members contribute capital, use products and services and contribute labor to the cooperative.

Associate members contribute capital is a member who only contributes capital, does not use products and services of the cooperative and does not contribute labor to the cooperative.

Income distribution to official members is based on the following two levels: (i) the level of product and service usage of members is the ratio of the value of products and services used by each member to the total value of products and services provided by the cooperative to all members; (ii) The level of labor contribution of members is measured by the ratio of salary, wages or remuneration of each member to the total salary, wages and remuneration of all members (National Assembly of the Socialist Republic of Vietnam, 2023).

Labor contribution is the direct participation of members in management and labor according to the agreement at the cooperative. Income distribution to capital-contributing associate members is based on: capital contribution is the value of contributed assets that a member has contributed or committed to contribute to the charter capital of the cooperative or the value of assets that a member has contributed or committed to contribute to the cooperative group according to the provisions of the cooperation contract. Capital contribution is the contribution of assets by members to form the charter capital when establishing the cooperative or to supplement the charter capital of an established cooperative.

Applying Legal Regulations on Income Distribution in Cooperatives

Long My Safe Vegetable Production Cooperative. Address: No. 16 San Cu Street, San Cu Hamlet, Long Thanh Bac Ward, Hoa Thanh Town, Tay Ninh Province, established on October 11, 2017. Business line is safe vegetable production (Long My Safe Vegetable Production Cooperative, 2017)

Charter capital of VND 100,000,000. The cooperative has 7 official members with capital contribution and capital contribution ratio (Long My Safe Vegetable Production Cooperative, 2017).

Table 1. Capital Contribution and Capital Contribution Ratio

Unit: Dong

Numerical order	Official Member	Value of capital contribution	Proportion
1	Nguyen Thanh Binh	10.000.000	10%
2	Nguyen Van Bao	15.000.000	15%
3	Nguyen Thanh Hung	15.000.000	15%
4	Le Van Thuan	10.000.000	10%
5	Pham Van Hai	10.000.000	10%
6	Le Huu Phuoc	20.000.000	20%
7	Nguyen Ngoc Anh	20.000.000	20%
	Total charter capital	100.000.000	100%

Source: Author

Members have contributed enough capital, the capital contribution ratio of each member does not exceed 30% of the charter capital.

The Cooperative Charter stipulates that the undivided General Fund deduction ratio is 20% of income from internal transactions, the Bonus Fund deduction ratio is 10%, the Welfare Fund deduction ratio is 10%, 60% is distributed to official members according to the level of product usage and labor contribution, 40% is distributed to official members according to the capital contribution ratio (Long My Safe Vegetable Production Cooperative, 2025).

In case the Cooperative has two or more products or services, the product and service ratio is divided according to the level of product

and service usage first, then divided to members according to each product and service.

The Charter is in accordance with the provisions of the 2023 Law on Cooperatives on the rate of fund deduction, the rate of income distribution and the rate of capital contribution of each member.

The General Assembly of Cooperative members unanimously elected Mr. Nguyen Thanh Binh as the legal representative with the title of director, and elected Mr. Nguyen Van Bao as the controller

Information on business activities in 2024 is as follows:

Table 2. Revenue from Internal Transactions is as Follows

Unit: Dong

Numerical order	Official Member	Value of using cooperative products	Proportion
1	Nguyen Thanh Binh	300.000.000	30%
2	Nguyen Van Bao	100.000.000	10%
3	NguyenThanh Hung	0	0%
4	Le Van Thuan	200.000.000	20%
5	Pham Van Hai	50.000.000	5%
6	Le Huu Phuoc	150.000.000	15%
7	Nguyen Ngoc Anh	200.000.000	20%
	Total revenue	1.000.000.000	100%

Source: Author's preparation

Table 3. Business Performance Results in 2024

Unit: Dong

Numerical order	Target	Code	Amount	Remaining value
1	Internal transaction revenue	(01)	1.000.000.000	
2	Internal transaction costs	(02)	900.000.000	
3	Income from insider trading	(03) = (01) - (02)	100.000.000	
4	Extract from undivided common fund as prescribed by the Charter 20%	(04)	20.000.000	80.000.000
5	Corporate income tax	(05)	Tax Free	80.000.000
6	Other financial obligations	(06)	0	80.000.000
7	Loss carried forward from 2023	(07)	30.000.000	50.000.000
8	Deduct funds according to legal regulations (if any)	(08)	0	50.000.000
9	Other fund allocation: 10% bonus fund	(09)	5.000.000	45.000.000
10	Other fund allocation: welfare fund 10%	(10)	5.000.000	40.000.000

11	Distribute 60% to official members according to product usage and labor contribution level.	(11) = (10) x 60%	24.000.000	16.000.000
12	Distribute 40% according to the capital contribution ratio of official members	(12) = (10) x 40%	16.000.000	0

Source: Author prepared

According to legal regulations, the remaining value must be distributed at least 51% to official members according to the level of product usage and labor contribution.

First, the cooperative decided to distribute 60% to official members according to the level of product usage and labor contribution in accordance with legal regulations with the amount of 24,000,000 VND. In which:

(i) The cooperative decides to distribute 70% according to the level of product usage with the amount of VND 24,000,000 x 70% = VND 16,800,000, the distribution level for one dong of revenue from internal transactions is VND 16,800,000/1,000,000,000 = VND 0.0168

(ii) The cooperative decides to distribute 30% according to the level of labor contribution with

the amount of VND 24,000,000 x 30% = VND 7,200,000, the distribution level for one dong of salary on the total salary of members directly involved in management is VND 7,200,000/180,000,000 = VND 0.04.

The total salary in 2024 is VND 250,000,000. In which, the salary of official members participating in the management of the cooperative of Mr. Nguyen Thanh Binh and Mr. Nguyen Van Bao is 180,000,000 VND

Second, the cooperative decided to distribute 40% of the remaining income according to the capital contribution ratio with the amount of 16,000,000 VND, the distribution level for one capital contribution is 16,000,000 VND/100,000,000 VND = 0.16 VND

Table 4. Income Distribution for Official Members According to the Level of Product Usage and the Level of Labor Contribution

Unit: Dong

Numerical order	Official Member	Usage level	Dividend	Total amount	Labor contribution level	Dividend	Total amount
1	Nguyen Thanh Binh	300.000.000	0.0168	5.040.000	120.000.000	0.04	4.800.000
2	Nguyen Van Bao	100.000.000	0.0168	1.680.000	60.000.000	0.04	2.400.000
3	Nguyen Thanh Hung	0	0.0168	0			
4	Le Van Thuan	200.000.000	0.0168	3.360.000			
5	Pham Van Hai	50.000.000	0.0168	840.000			
6	Le Huu Phuoc	150.000.000	0.0168	2.520.000			
7	Nguyen Ngoc Anh	200.000.000	0.0168	3.360.000			
	Total	1.000.000.000		16.800.000	180.000.000		7.200.000

Source: Author's

Table 5. Distribution by Capital Contribution Ratio

Unit: Dong

Numerical order	Official Member	Value of capital contribution	Dividend	Total amount
1	Nguyen Thanh Binh	10.000.000	0.16	1.600.000

2	Nguyen Van Bao	15.000.000	0.16	2.400.000
3	Nguyen Thanh Hung	15.000.000	0.16	2.400.000
4	Le Van Thuan	10.000.000	0.16	1.600.000
5	Pham Van Hai	10.000.000	0.16	1.600.000
6	Le Huu Phuoc	20.000.000	0.16	3.200.000
7	Nguyen Ngoc Anh	20.000.000	0.16	3.200.000
	Total charter capital	100.000.000		16.000.000

Source: Author

Total income distribution is $16,800,000 + 7,200,000 + 16,000,000 = 40,000,000$ VND

Comments on income distribution

Advantages

First: General principles

Cooperatives are a type of collective economy, members share benefits with each other, contribute capital, contribute efforts, use goods and services of the cooperative and enjoy the results together, these are the principles: voluntary participation and expansion of links; democracy, equality in organization and management; responsibility to participate in economic activities of cooperative members; autonomy and self-responsibility.

Second: Distribution according to capital contribution

The cooperative has distributed income according to the capital contribution stated in the Charter, this is the primary source of capital, together with other mobilized capital sources used in the business process to generate income for the cooperative.

If the cooperative operates effectively, members with financial capacity will contribute more charter capital, but not more than 30% of the charter capital, both creating a source of capital for the cooperative to use in the business process and distributing income from the contributed capital. On the contrary, if the cooperative operates ineffectively, incurs losses leading to bankruptcy, members will be responsible for limited liability within their capital contribution, this is the investment principle in business.

Third: Distribution according to the level of labor contribution

Distribution of income according to the level of labor contribution aims to encourage members to contribute labor directly to participate in management and labor in the cooperative, depending on each job position corresponding to their capacity and labor achievements, both receiving salary and distributing income based on that achievement is salary, this is the principle of redistribution

Fourth: Distribution according to the level of product use

Distribution of income according to the level of product use aims to encourage members to directly use the cooperative's products, creating revenue, the final result is to create cooperative profits. Members who use a lot of products will be distributed a lot of income, members who use less products will be distributed a little income, members who do not use products will not be distributed any income, this is the traditional principle of the cooperative, demonstrating the nature of the cooperative.

Disadvantages

One is: Distribution of income according to the proportion of capital contribution. The cooperative bases its income distribution on the capital contribution and capital contribution ratio of previous years as the basis for this year and the following years, which is unreasonable. Second: Distributing the remaining 60% of income to official members according to the level of product use and the level of labor contribution, but the Charter does not specify the level of product use in the total of 60%; the level of labor contribution in the total of 60%. In fact, when distributing, the Director decides 70% according to the level of product use, 30% according to the level of labor contribution because Director Nguyen Thanh Binh is the person who uses the most products (see Table 4)

Proposal to Improve Legal Regulations on Income Distribution

Based on the above shortcomings, the author has two recommendations as follows:

First: Regarding the value of members' capital contributions

(i). The cooperative converts the value of members' capital contributions to the actual value of the current fiscal year according to the principle of multiplying the value of capital contributions (x) by the inflation rate of the years from the year of capital contribution;

(ii) Every year, the Board of Directors establishes a Council to re-evaluate the value of capital contributions or hires a consultant to determine the capital contribution conversion coefficient as a basis for distribution.

Second: Regarding income distribution to official members according to the level of product usage and labor contribution. Cooperatives need to clearly stipulate the ratio in the Charter or in the financial regulations, approved by the General Meeting of Members

Conclusion

In order to ensure the sustainable, stable and long-term development of cooperatives, and to improve their competitiveness in the market, the regulations on income distribution to members are one of the important regulations, contributing to attracting members to join the cooperative. Income distribution to members needs to harmoniously combine the benefits between distribution methods with two subjects: cooperatives and members. The charter and financial regulations of cooperatives are detailed, public and transparent, making the calculation of income and distribution more convenient.

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